

The main reason for why the Euler product not equal to the Zeta function

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Abstract: The author of this article has already disproved the Euler product equal to the Riemann zeta function that was proved by the earlier mathematicians. This article presents the main reason for why the Euler product not equal to the Riemann zeta function.

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1. Introduction

The Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s)$ for all complex numbers such as $s = a + ib$ is defined by

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-s} = 1^{-s} + 2^{-s} + 3^{-s} + 4^{-s} + 5^{-s} + \dots, \quad \forall \Re(s) > 1. \quad (1)$$

Where $\Re(s)$ is the real part of all complex numbers.

2. Proof of the Earlier Mathematicians

The earlier mathematicians proved the Euler product equal to the Riemann zeta function [1-4] as follows

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_i^s}}, \quad (2)$$

where $\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 - p_i^{-s}}$ is the Euler product and p_i is the i^{th} prime.

The Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = 1 + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \frac{1}{8^s} + \frac{1}{9^s} \dots$

$$\frac{1}{2^s} \zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{8^s} + \frac{1}{10^s} + \frac{1}{12^s} + \frac{1}{14^s} + \frac{1}{16^s} + \dots$$

$$\zeta(s) - \frac{1}{2^s} \zeta(s) = 1 + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \frac{1}{9^s} + \frac{1}{11^s} + \frac{1}{13^s} + \frac{1}{15^s} + \frac{1}{17^s} + \dots$$

$$i.e., \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s}\right) \zeta(s) = 1 + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \frac{1}{9^s} + \frac{1}{11^s} + \frac{1}{13^s} + \frac{1}{15^s} + \dots$$

$$\frac{1}{3^s} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s}\right) \zeta(s) = \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{9^s} + \frac{1}{15^s} + \frac{1}{21^s} + \frac{1}{27^s} + \frac{1}{33^s} + \frac{1}{39^s} + \frac{1}{45^s} + \dots$$

$$\left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s}\right) \zeta(s) - \frac{1}{3^s} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s}\right) \zeta(s) = 1 + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \frac{1}{11^s} + \frac{1}{13^s} + \frac{1}{17^s} + \dots$$

$$i.e., \left(1 - \frac{1}{3^s}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s}\right) \zeta(s) = 1 + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \frac{1}{11^s} + \frac{1}{13^s} + \frac{1}{17^s} + \frac{1}{19^s} + \dots$$

If the above processes are continued, the multiples of prime factors such as 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, ..., are removed.

$$\dots\dots\dots \left(1 - \frac{1}{13^s}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{11^s}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{7^s}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{5^s}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{3^s}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^s}\right) \zeta(s) = 1. \quad (3)$$

$$i.e., \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_k^s}\right) \zeta(s) = 1 \Rightarrow \zeta(s) = \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p_k^s}\right)}.$$

3. Disproof by the Author of this Article

The author of this article disproves the Euler product equal to the Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s)$ that was proved by the earlier mathematicians.

If $s = 1$, then $\zeta(1)$ denotes the harmonic series.

$$\zeta(1) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{7} + \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{9} + \frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{11} + \frac{1}{12} + \dots \quad (4)$$

Also, by substituting $s = 1$ in Equation (3), we obtain

$$\dots \times \frac{10}{11} \times \frac{6}{7} \times \frac{4}{5} \times \frac{2}{3} \times \frac{1}{2} \zeta(1) = 1 \Rightarrow \zeta(1) = \frac{2}{1} \times \frac{3}{2} \times \frac{5}{4} \times \frac{7}{6} \times \frac{11}{10} \times \dots = \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i}\right)}. \quad (5)$$

From the equations (4) and (5), $\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i}\right)} > \zeta(1)$ obviously.

Similarly, we compute the Euler product for the Riemann zeta function for $s = 2$ as follows. The Basel problem [8] indicates that $\zeta(2) \cong 1.644934$.

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i^2}\right)} = \frac{4}{3} \times \frac{9}{8} \times \frac{25}{24} \times \frac{49}{48} \times \frac{121}{120} \times \dots > 2 \text{ and } \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i^2}\right)} > \zeta(2).$$

If we continue the above process upto $s = n$,

If we continue the above process upto $s = n$, then $\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i^n}\right)} > \zeta(n)$

$$\therefore \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i^s}\right)} > \zeta(s)$$

Form the above result, we conclude that the Euler product is not equal to the Riemann zeta function.

4. The Main Reason for Wrong Proof by the Earlier Mathematicians

In two infinite series, we must apply arithmetic operations, such as addition and subtraction, only on the corresponding numbers to get the resultant series rightly. Otherwise, the resultant series might be obtained wrongly.

For instance, let us consider the following infinite series (harmonic series):

$$S = 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{7} + \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{9} + \frac{1}{10} + \dots \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}S = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{12} + \frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{16} + \frac{1}{18} + \dots \quad (7)$$

In Series (6) and Series (7), to applying the arithmetic operation 'subtraction' on the corresponding numbers as follows:

$$S - \frac{1}{2}S = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{4}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{6}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{8}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{5} - \frac{1}{10}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{6} - \frac{1}{12}\right) + \dots \quad (8)$$

$$\text{The resultant series: } \frac{1}{2}S = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{12} + \dots \quad (9)$$

The arithmetic operation on Series (8) is the right process. So, the resultant series (9) is true.

In Series (6) and Series (7), to applying the arithmetic operation 'subtraction' without the corresponding numbers as follows:

$$S - \frac{1}{2}S = 1 + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}\right) + \frac{1}{3} + \left(\frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{4}\right) + \frac{1}{5} + \left(\frac{1}{6} - \frac{1}{6}\right) + \frac{1}{7} + \dots \quad (10)$$

$$\text{The resultant series: } \frac{1}{2}S = 1 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{7} + \frac{1}{9} + \frac{1}{11} + \dots \quad (11)$$

The arithmetic operation on Series (10) is the wrong process. So, the resultant series (11) is false.

Note that the sum of Series (11) is greater than the sum of Series (9).

Therefore, the proof for the Euler product equal to the Riemann zeta function is false because the earlier mathematicians had followed the arithmetic operation on Series (10).

This is the main reason for why the Euler product not equal to the Zeta function.

5. Conclusion

In the article, the author has disproved the Euler product representation for the Riemann zeta function that was proved by the earlier mathematicians.

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